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IN BACOR CITY, CAVITE**

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Filipino Trending TikTok on Outfit Ideas, Lifestyle Influence and Factors on Body Image of Selected Young Adults in Bacoor City, Cavite

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Abstract

The purpose of study is to identify the correlation between watching Filipino trending TikTok outfit ideas to the aspects of body image and its lifestyle influence, particularly among young adults in Bacoor, Cavite. Body image refers to a person's interpretation of their physical image and emotions and feelings. The said aspects are perceptual, affective, and cognitive. To ensure the anonymity of respondents regarding personal information, we provide consent forms to the young adult participants in Bacoor, Cavite. All respondents who are TikTok users were chosen using random sampling to achieve the desired findings. Pearson's R correlation was used to determine the statistics and the correlation in the study. With regards with the demographics, there is no significant difference between males and females when it comes to body image. Results showed that affective body image is significantly correlated with perceptual and cognitive body image. Perceptual body image is significantly correlated with cognitive body image. Lastly, affective, perceptual, and cognitive body image is correlated with the influence of TikTok.

Keywords: *affective body image, aspect, behavioral body image, body image, TikTok*

Introduction

The development of the world's technology has been rapidly evolving; from newspapers and shipment of letters to wired telephones and payphones, the idea of connecting people and sharing information is the central concept as to why the development of social networking sites has been made into reality. The advances in social media like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok have been popular to use as a platform to give people ways to share their state and whatever comes into their minds, look at other people's posts and react to them, and share their interests with their friends and even the world. It has come to the point where market trends tend to follow what is popular online: the rise of "aesthetic" minimalism and viral trends; social media opened paths to connect people through similarities in interest.

The social media platform TikTok was launched in September 2016 that allows users to create, watch and share short clips on people's respective mobile phones. The social media application TikTok encourages creative videos with the user's expressing their style, which people can view and like if it is with their interest. With people seeing and watching videos that are align with their interests, users can utilize the duet or stitch feature on the app, which results in more engagement and becomes a talk or trend in TikTok. The TikTok platform has created fun and elevated levels of engagement mainly because of its features that can do collaborative videos with additions or features like pieces of music, stickers, backgrounds, and more.

With the COVID-19 lockdown and people stuck in their homes without anything to do, people used TikTok, and it eventually became one of the fastest-growing social media applications. As of 2022, the Philippines has an estimated 40.4 million active users on TikTok, with users aged eighteen and above as the most abundant users (datareportal, 2022). With people using the said platform and watching almost any video online, the time spent by consumers causes social commerce to be one of the fastest-growing trends in the Philippines, and TikTok is expected to support the social commerce sector in the said country.

The TikTok algorithm is curated in accordance with the users' interests and the videos they liked while strolling through their For You Page (FYP). The amount of user interaction on certain topics and videos, comments, and share links, the TikTok algorithm app recommends videos with similarities that the users may like, and that makes a particular discussion circulate on TikTok and eventually becomes a trending topic. One example is the Y2K fashion that made a comeback this year. With the hashtag #Y2KFashion, the 2000s throwback fashion and retro clothes have more than fifty-eight million hits and are still progressively growing. Users have been incorporating the style trend with their wardrobe, and numerous TikTok videos have been made that are inspired and aligned with the trending fashion content.

A lot of different fashion content has been produced in TikTok that users may incorporate into their wardrobe style or get inspiration from it. Such videos are like clothing shopping haul, where many TikTok content creators highlight new outfits that can be mixed and matched with their other clothes. This can encourage users to buy and look for similar outfits that suit them, with lower prices or similar clothing styles. Influencers like high-fashion models have been used to recreate their style and dress like them.

Despite the beauty and the growing trend in fashion, there are still negative influences that TikTok can have on a person's sense of self and body. Such trend "is it fashion or is she just skinny?" explores the fashion trends and whether it is made for women of all sizes or only model-like figures. Certain fashion trends are not flattering to people with different body sizes, and outfits do not fit a person's plus sized or even mid-sized body. The TikTok algorithm is not always positive in accordance with the users' interests or likes. With its adverse effects, some would go through extreme lengths to change their physical appearance and try to copy the image they see on

such TikTok videos. The body image concerns affect them in an adverse way as they try to achieve the perceived body on the video, regardless of the process which can be utterly dangerous to their health and not recommended. In a study by Congqiao (2021), people, mostly young adults, would go on extremely unhealthy diets and some will even get cosmetic surgery just to achieve their desired results.

The promotion of fashion trends can make people question themselves, how they dress, and their figure. With the outfits in the videos, users can have body image problems and physical dissatisfaction. Comparisons are made whenever they watch certain videos of trends, and a decline in self-worth can affect their thinking and behavior about their body image (Hulsing, 2021). Fashion trends on TikTok are fun and always changing; it gives people a broad spectrum of ideas about how they will dress. Nonetheless, the fashion content trends seen on TikTok can adversely or favorably impact the user's body image and influence their lifestyle.

With this concern, the impact of Filipino TikTok fashion content on lifestyle influence, and on the factors of body image, were studied. This study also aims to provide suitable approaches with regards to body image and other recommendations based on the study's findings.

This study concerns on Filipino Trending TikTok on Outfit ideas, lifestyle influence and factors on body image of selected young adults in Bacoor, Cavite. TikTok is a huge platform for everyone, particularly young adults. TikTok is one of the fastest-growing social media networks, allowing users to record and share short videos ranging from fifteen (15) seconds to one (1) minute in length (Web, 2021). Because of the trend, different outfit contents are extremely relevant, and some of them are impacted by imitating or getting outfit inspiration. However, it may have positive and negative effects on the young, depending on how they perceive themselves in relation to the TikTok video they are viewing.

TikTok is a social media app that uses video to share content, and the majority of young people use it for fun. A person's body image is influenced by what they see in social media apps like TikTok; it changes their point of view when they see an ideal way of life, a beautiful body, and a perfect relationship without assessing the stories behind those things. TikTok is an incredible platform where anybody may publish videos to give the audience the simplest way to present themselves. In the Philippines, much of the trend is outfit ideas content, and TikTok is one of the best platforms for publishing videos. Young adults are mostly interested in watching fashion content on TikTok. This content is popular in the West, and the Philippines has followed suit; for example, Fit Check content is popular in the Philippines. With the trend and influence of TikTok influencers, many young adults are particularly interested in fashion content.

The Outfit Ideas started to become popular because of the influencer's posting of video and picture content. With most youth being interested in outfit fashion trends; they are the primary target audience for some social media apps with fashion content creators. When they feel fashionable, their body image improves, and they feel more confident. Wearing any outfit ideas that people are comfortable with will make them feel perfect in the mirror, but some young people may see themselves as inferior. This outfit ideas can positively or negatively impact someone's body image; it can help them boost their confidence and see their body image as beautiful and good enough, or it can make them feel like they do not meet the standard of beauty, resulting in low confidence. Outfit consciousness is growing daily, and everyone wants to appear their best. Looking beautiful is almost no harm unless you get obsessed with fashion. It is undeniably true that today's generations want to be in the trend because of an endlessly changing new trend. People, especially youth, want to go with the trend. It is up to the person how you want to present yourself and build your future.

One aspect of body image is how a person perceives oneself. Their size, appealing characteristics, and those you believe are less desirable. Every individual is born with unchanging qualities representing their body image, such as how they dress and what style fits them. Furthermore, if you see that your self-image is unrealistic, the traits and styles of others will mirror your self-concept. One of the four components of body image is how you perceive yourself—this is your “perceptual body image.” Your “affective body image” is how you feel about how you appear. The ideas and beliefs you have about your body—this is your “cognitive body image”—and, finally, your actions in relation to your appearance—your “behavioral body image” (Amy L. 2021).

The lifestyle influence and factors on a young adult may be good or bad; it depends on how they interpret the TikTok video trend they watched. Some people may benefit because it helps them accept and be satisfied with their bodies, and it boosts their self-esteem by influencing or adopting the trend they are watching, which inspires them to explore and try new things. Following outfit trends has the potential to make you more popular. In reality, many individuals in modern culture view outfit to express themselves as well as look attractive (Andreas, 2022). While the negative effect of negative body image is dissatisfaction and the desire to be someone else because they are not content with who they are, how they interpret the outfit trend video may result from feeling down, having anxiety, and trying hard to be with someone. Majority of women blame their own physique for clothing that are ill-fitting for them, and this can negatively affect one's physical image, self-esteem, and sense of self. Unrealistic media images displayed on sites like Instagram and TikTok enable society to broadcast messages that associate thinness with attractiveness and health, as stated in the Fashion Industry and Body Image report (2021).

Research Questions

This study aims to examine the correlation of watching Filipino Trending TikTok outfit ideas on the aspects of body image and lifestyle influence of young adults residing in Bacoor City. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents when they will be grouped according to:
 - 1.1. Sex
2. What is the perceived level of body image based on the following:
 - 2.1. Affective,
 - 2.2. Perceptual,
 - 2.3. Cognitive?
3. Is there a significant difference between male and female respondents in terms of:
 - 3.1. Affective
 - 3.2. Perceptual
 - 3.3. Cognitive
 - 3.4. TikTok Influence?
4. Is there a significant correlation among factors such as affective, perceptual, cognitive and in the TikTok Influence?

Methodology

Research Design

The researchers employed descriptive correlational research as a research design to measure the relationship between both variables. A correlational study determines whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more variables within a population or sample (Apuke, 2017). The researchers utilized the correlational design to describe the relationship between watching Filipino trending TikTok outfit ideas and the aspects of body image and its' lifestyle influence.

Respondents

Table 1. *Frequency Distribution of Respondents*

Demographic Profile		Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	49	49
	Female	51	51
	Total	100	100

The table above shows the Frequency Distribution of Respondents. At sex, forty-nine percent (49%) are male respondents and fifty-one percent (51%) are female respondents. Hence based on the results, there are more female respondents compared to male respondents.

A total of hundred (100) respondents from the city of Bacoor voluntarily participated in this study. The criteria for respondents are their demographic profile-- sex, TikTok users, or do have an account and are interested in watching trending TikTok outfit ideas. With the help of social media friends, the survey questionnaire is shared from different social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Messenger.

Random sampling method was used in this study to gather respondents as this study's participants are random selection of a small subset of individuals or members from a larger group. The study's participants were Filipino who are young adults in Bacoor city of Cavite that has a TikTok account and is interested in watching trending TikTok outfit ideas. The respondents' data are subjected to the frequency of watching Filipino trending TikTok outfit ideas and the aspects of body image.

Instrument

In this study, the researchers used a self-made questionnaire and constructed a test that measured the degree of relationship of watching TikTok outfit ideas, its influence, and the scores of the respondents in the aspects of body image. The researchers conducted a test that consisted of statements that identifies the correlation between watching TikTok outfit ideas, its lifestyle influence, and their aspects of body image, followed by checking the reliability and validity of the said self-made questionnaire.

Procedure

To accomplish the study's objectives, the following procedures were followed in collecting data and management: The documents were first processed by the thesis advisor, the establishment, and the research participants to obtain their insights. The researchers used descriptive correlational and random sampling methods to measure the relationship between watching Filipino TikTok Outfit Ideas to the three aspects of body image as well as its lifestyle influence. Also, researchers will use self-made tools to gather the respondents' data and use Google Forms for the questionnaire.

The target respondents of the researchers are people who watch TikTok outfit ideas that were required for the study. The survey questionnaire was posted on the social media platforms TikTok, and other social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram.

The researchers' survey questionnaire contains the necessary information for the respondents' understanding of the study. The researchers followed R.A. #10173, the Data Policy Act of 2012. An act was enacted to protect individual personal information and communications systems in the government and private sector, establishing a national privacy commission for this purpose and other

purposes (Congress of the Philippines, Metro Manila, Fifteenth Congress) to ensure the safety of respondents' personal information.

Data Analysis

Frequency Distribution. Used in getting a graphical representation of the number of individuals in each category in the measurement scale.

Pearson-r. After getting the mean, or the average score on personal growth and tendency to compare socially, the researchers used Pearson-R to assess a hypothesis by examining the correlation of the two variables.

Results and Discussion

SOP 2: What is the perceived level of the respondent's body image based on the following: Affective, Perceptual Cognitive

Table 2. Mean Score per Factor

Sex	Factor	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Male	Affective	4.49	0.98	Strongly Agree	Very High Affective
	Perceptual	4.36	1.35	Strongly Agree	Very High Perceptual
	Cognitive	3.97	1.12	Agree	High Cognitive
	Influence	4.46	1.24	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
Female	Affective	4.51	0.89	Strongly Agree	Very High Affective
	Perceptual	4.40	1.05	Strongly Agree	Very High Perceptual
	Cognitive	4.06	0.65	Agree	High Cognitive
	Influence	4.48	0.94	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence
Overall	Affective	4.50	0.92	Strongly Agree	Very High Affective
	Perceptual	4.39	1.17	Strongly Agree	Very High Perceptual
	Cognitive	4.03	0.86	Agree	High Cognitive
	Influence	4.47	1.06	Strongly Agree	Very High Influence

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree/ Very High; 3.40-4.19= Agree/High; 2.60-3.39= Neutral/Uncertain; 1.80-2.59= Disagree/Low; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree/Very Low

Table above shows the mean score per factor for both male and female respondents. For male respondents, the affective mean score is 4.49 (SD= 0.98) with a verbal description of strongly agree and verbal interpretation of "Very High Affective". The perceptual mean score is 4.36 (SD= 1.35) with a verbal description of strongly agree and verbal interpretation of "Very High Perceptual". The Cognitive mean score is 3.97 (SD= 1.12) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High Cognitive". The Influence mean score is 4.46 (SD= 1.24) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Very High Influence".

For female respondents, the affective mean score is 4.51 (SD= 0.89) with a verbal description of strongly agree and verbal interpretation of "Very High Affective". The perceptual mean score is 4.40 (SD= 1.05) with a verbal description of strongly agree and verbal interpretation of "Very High Perceptual". The Cognitive mean score is 4.06 (SD= 0.65) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High Cognitive". The Influence mean score is 4.48 (SD= 0.94) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Very High Influence".

The overall affective mean score is 4.50 (SD= 0.92) with a verbal description of strongly agree and verbal interpretation of "Very High Affective". The overall perceptual mean score is 4.39 (SD= 1.17) with a verbal description of strongly agree and verbal interpretation of "Very High Perceptual". The overall Cognitive mean score is 4.03 (SD= 0.86) with a verbal description of "Agree" and verbal interpretation of "High Cognitive". The overall Influence mean score is 4.47 (SD= 1.06) with a verbal description of "Strongly Agree" and verbal interpretation of "Very High Influence".

SOP 3: Is there a significant difference between male and female respondents in terms of: Affective, Perceptual, Cognitive, Influence?

Table 3. Test for Significant Difference

Factor	p-value	Significant	Ho Decision
Affective	0.892	Not Significant	Accept
Perceptual	0.890	Not Significant	Accept
Cognitive	0.635	Not Significant	Accept
Influence	0.940	Not Significant	Accept

*Significant at .05 alpha level

Table above shows the test for significant difference between male and female respondents across factors such as affective, perceptual, cognitive and influence. For affective, the computed p-value is 0.892 which is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there

is no significant difference in terms of affective between male and female respondents and null hypothesis is accepted. For perceptual, the computed p-value is 0.890 which is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in terms of perceptual between male and female respondents and null hypothesis is accepted. For cognitive, the computed p-value is 0.635 which is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in terms of cognitive between male and female respondents and null hypothesis is accepted. For influence, the computed p-value is 0.940 which is greater than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is no significant difference in terms of influence between male and female respondents and null hypothesis is accepted.

Contrary to expectations that social media such as TikTok has negative effects to the body image, the findings showed that young women who were exposed to positive body image content on TikTok, such as messages about body acceptance and diversity, were more satisfied with their bodies, less likely to compare themselves to others, and had better moods. Additionally, young women reported increased body satisfaction and a more upbeat mood when they shared content on TikTok that was supportive of their positive body image. TikTok has likewise turned into a stage for promoting body inspiration and self-love. Numerous TikTok creators produce content that encourages them to embrace their bodies and celebrate their unique qualities, rather than focusing on viewers' perceived flaws. For individuals who experience feelings of isolation or marginalization as a result of their body type, TikTok can offer a sense of community and belonging. Users can share their own stories and connect with others who have had similar experiences, which can help alleviate feelings of body shame and embarrassment. Also, people of all shapes, sizes, and backgrounds can now share their experiences and stories on TikTok, including their struggles with body image. As a result, representations of various body types have become more varied, and acceptance of different body types has increased. The authors suggest that people who struggle with body dissatisfaction can use social media platforms like TikTok to promote a positive body image and find social support.

According to Tiggemann and Slater (2014), women's perceptual and affective body image improved when they were exposed to diverse body types as opposed to traditional media depictions of thin models. One more study by Bucchianeri et al. (2018) discovered that women who reported feeling satisfied with their body size and shape had higher levels of self-esteem and positive affect, whereas women who reported feeling dissatisfied with their bodies had higher levels of negative affect.

A measure of attitudinal body image with affective and perceptual components was the goal of the study conducted by Brown, Cash, and Mikulka (1990). The researchers regulated the Body-Self Relations Questionnaire (BSRQ) to an example of undergrads and found that the survey things could be gathered into seven variables, including appearance evaluation, body areas satisfaction, and affective perspectives. The researchers found that the affective perspectives factor was firmly related with different variables, especially appearance assessment and body areas satisfaction. This suggests that people tend to have a more negative perceptual body image as well as a more negative affective body image.

In a sample of college women, Keery, van den Berg, and Thompson (2004) found that higher levels of body satisfaction were associated with more accurate perceptions of body size and shape. Although the relationship between affective and cognitive aspects of body image can be complicated and varies from person to person, research suggests that these two aspects generally have a positive correlation. This truly means that as full of feeling self-perception (e.g., body fulfillment) increments, mental self-perception (e.g., precise view of body size and shape) likewise will in general increment.

Vogel, E.A., Rose, J.P., Okdie, B.M., Eckles, K., & Franz, B (2015) In this study, the researchers examined the relationship between social media use, affective body image, and self-esteem over a period of six months in a sample of college students. They found that individuals who reported lower affective body image at the beginning of the study were less likely to use social media six months later, even after controlling baseline levels of social media use and self-esteem. The researchers suggested that this finding may be due to the fact that individuals with lower affective body image may feel more vulnerable to negative social comparison and criticism on social media, leading them to avoid or limit their use of these platforms. However, the study also found that social media use was not a significant predictor of changes in affective body image or self-esteem over time.

Tylka, T. L., & Wilcox, J. A. (2006) Researchers examined the effects of a body acceptance intervention on women's body image in a study that was published in the Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology. The women had a negative body image. Through body exposure exercises and cognitive restructuring strategies, the eight weekly sessions of the intervention focused on enhancing perceptual body image. Both perceptual and cognitive body image significantly improved in the intervention-completed participants, as evidenced by lower levels of body-related anxiety, dissatisfaction, and satisfaction. The authors came to the conclusion that body acceptance interventions may be effective in promoting positive body image and that improving perceptual body image can result in positive changes in cognitive body image.

SOP 4: Is there a significant correlation among factors such as affective, perceptual, cognitive and influence?

Table above shows the test for correlations among aforementioned factors such as affective, perceptual, cognitive and influence. For affective correlated with perceptual, the computed R-value is 0.657 which is interpreted as Moderate Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level.

This would mean that there is significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as affective increases, perceptual also increases.

Table 4. Test for Correlations

Correlated Factors	R-value	Interpretation	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision	
Perceptual	0.657	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000*	Significant	Reject	
Affective	Cognitive	0.593	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000*	Significant	Reject
	Influence	0.568	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000*	Significant	Reject
Perceptual	Cognitive	0.598	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000*	Significant	Reject
	Influence	0.734	High Positive Correlation	0.000*	Significant	Reject
Cognitive	Influence	0.540	Moderate Positive Correlation	0.000*	Significant	Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level/.90-1.00= Very High Correlation; .70 to .90 = High Correlation; .50 to .70 = Moderate Correlation; .30 to .50= Low Correlation; .00 to .30 = Negligible Correlation

According to the study of Congqiao (2021), body image adversely affects young adults as they try to mimic what they perceive on TikTok and would go extreme lengths to achieve such. The result does not support this study for the reason that as the respondents become more positive when it comes to their feelings, the more they are likely to positively perceive themselves.

For affective correlated with cognitive, the computed R-value is 0.593 which is interpreted as Moderate Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as affective increases, cognitive also increases.

Affective body image is your feelings about your body (Johnson, 2022), and the Cognitive body image is our thoughts about our body (Lauder, 2021). These two are correlated with each other for the reason that in order for a person to know her thoughts about herself, she should know first what she feels about her body, and by that, the cognitive body image will be affected, the result supports the study of Lauder (2021), in which she says that Affective body image will likely reflect either satisfaction or dissatisfaction about your weight, shape, or other various aesthetics (Lauder, 2021) which is basically our cognitive body image.

For affective correlated with influence, the computed R-value is 0.568 which is interpreted as Moderate Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as affective increases, influence also increases.

Contrary to the study of Korbani and LaBrie, with the given rise of social media, body image dissatisfaction increased among young adults, which led to adverse consequences such as eating disorders. This result shows otherwise as respondents are more positive about their feelings, the influence of TikTok influences them positively as well.

For perceptual correlated with cognitive, the computed R-value is 0.598 which is interpreted as Moderate Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as perceptual increases, cognitive also increases.

According to Amy (2021), perceptual body image refers to how an individual perceives themselves. On the other hand, cognitive body image refers to the individual's ideas and beliefs about their body. The results indicate that perceptual body image is positive significantly correlated to cognitive body image. This result supports the previous study of Ouyang et al. (2020) that cognitive body image and body image are positively correlated with each other.

For perceptual correlated with influence, the computed R-value is 0.734 which is interpreted as High Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as perceptual increases, influence also increases.

Perceptual body image is the way you see your body (McShirley, 2023). This body image is significantly correlated with the influence of TikTok, for the reason that according to McNair (2022), it's hard to escape TikTok's endless stream of content, because its algorithm works differently, once it knows you enjoy seeing certain content, it shows you more of it, so in connection with perceptual body image, which is the way how you see yourself (Johnson, 2022). TikTok can be an instrument of it, we can use TikTok to get inspired and copy those styles and with the influence of TikTok, it can greatly impact on how we see ourselves, so Perceptual Body Image is significantly correlated to the TikTok influence.

Contrary to the study of Delaney (2021), which was centered to the consequences of usage of TikTok to people, it was stated that the TikTok platform encourages negative comparison, and in the study of people (na, 2022), especially young women who constantly compare themselves and make them adopt unhealthy diets, the results have showed otherwise.

For cognitive correlated with influence, the computed R-value is 0.540 which is interpreted as Moderate Positive Correlation with a p-value of 0.000 which is less than .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as cognitive increases, influence also increases.

The results indicate a moderately positive correlation between the cognitive body image and TikTok's Lifestyle Influence. Cognitive body image refers to an individual's belief and ideas about their own body image. On the other hand, TikTok does influence lifestyle in a way that it also affects the individual's thoughts about their body appearance. TikTok is one of the social media platforms that gives the ability to an individual to publicize and share the lifestyles and mindsets of a TikTok content creator that influences the audience's mind and beliefs (na, 2022). The data results supported the recent study of Hao et al. (2022) which the young adult individuals in city of Kuala Lumpur are using and suggesting using TikTok platform to engage more and increase their self-esteem because of its' positive effects on how they think about their body aspects.

Contrary to the study of Hulsing (2021), which stated that the social media application TikTok presents unattainable body standards, and this leads to internalization of the idea of being thin for females and being muscular for males. This result does not support the study as it showed that as the respondents become more positive when it comes to their ideas and beliefs towards their bodies, the more they are positively influenced by the TikTok outfit ideas.

Conclusions

Overall, the TikTok platform is significantly correlated to the aspect of body image (perceptual, affective, and cognitive) and influences the lifestyle among young adults regardless of sex.

The affective body image is moderately positively correlated with perceptual body image, cognitive body image and TikTok Lifestyle Influence. This means that as affective body image increases, perceptual also increases. As affective increases, cognitive also increases, and as affective increases, the influence also increases.

The Perceptual body image is moderate positively correlated with Cognitive body image and high positively correlated with TikTok Lifestyle Influence. This means that as perceptual increases, cognitive also increases and as perceptual increases, influence also increases.

Cognitive body image is moderately positively correlated with TikTok's Lifestyle Influence. This means that as cognitive increases, influence also increases.

The gathered data can be used by schools in reference for conducting seminars with the topic of TikTok being a tool for young adults' improvement with regard to their body image.

Future researchers may include one of the aspects of body image, which is the behavioral body image that was not included in this study due to reliability concern.

Future researchers may include the significant differences between the age bracket of young adults (18-25) and may choose other generations aside from young adults.

Future researchers may use different methods other than correlational to test the relationship between the aspects of body image and TikTok's Lifestyle Influence.

Future researchers can test for the other factors that influence young adults' lifestyle aside from the TikTok fashion outfit ideas.

Future researchers may explore and identify the other factors that influence young adults' lifestyle with other social networking sites or social media applications other than TikTok.

The researchers recommend continuing this study that includes larger sample sizes such as different age brackets and scope for broader results.

Young adults may help them become enlightened about the influences and factors on their body image and may help this study by sharing it with other youth to share the positive impact of the Filipino TikTok trend.

Researchers recommend this study to school establishments to enlighten those students on how to use social media apps like TikTok and have an in-depth explanation about how TikTok can not only have an adverse effect, but also give positive effects on their body image and lifestyle influences. This study may use them in some subjects like personality development, understanding the self, and other self-assessments.

Researchers recommend this study for TikTok users to use as guidance to avoid negative effects on their body image and lifestyle influences. TikTok has different content for different viewers, and this study may be used as their content to be able to spread awareness, especially since the result shows that TikTok, such as fashion outfit ideas, has a positive effect on their body image. his result can be their content to explain and enlighten the viewers.

Parents may use this study as their guidance to gain knowledge about the impact of TikTok in different types of content on their children. This study shows that when it comes to fashion, TikTok Trend has a good effect on their body image, and they will use it as their guide for their children to have a good effect on theirs.

Marketing ads can use this study as their guide to avoid the negative effects of their ads. We recommend also using this study to inform

their ads about the results, because not all social media apps have a negative effect, and to break the stereotype about social media. They can use the results in their ads, like putting this in their content.

In the psychology field, this may assist you in guiding when it comes to the effect of social media apps on a person's body image. You can also continue this study to answer more questions aside from the effect on their body image and lifestyle influences.

To the community, the researcher will recommend this study to help people to be able to spread awareness on different platforms and break the stereotype that social media always has a negative effect.

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